

PROCESS PARAMETERS INVESTIGATION ON THE FIBRE-MATRIX ADHESION OF CONTINUOUS FIBRES REINFORCED POLYTETRAFLUOROETHYLENE (PTFE)

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SUMMARY

This work presents a study of the manufacturing process and mechanical properties of composite laminates made of commercial PTFE with coated glass-fibre fabric. The experimental results indicate the most appropriate values for some of the manufacturing process parameters and the influence of these parameters on the interface fibre-matrix.

Keywords: PTFE, continuous fibres composites, interface fibre-matrix, process parameters, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

The weak chemical reactivity with other materials and very small coefficient of friction are some characteristics that become the PTFE a material of great interest to industry. However, these characteristics are also the main responsible for the poor adhesion between the fibre and matrix in composites using PTFE. These composites are made to improve some mechanical properties such as stiffness and strength, which are not so good for pure PTFE, as compared to engineering polymers and which limits the structural applications of PTFE.

The PTFE has a high molecular weight and therefore, high dynamic viscosity in the molten state, which makes its injection moulding to be a huge challenge. Thus, the manufacturing process of the PTFE is made by cold compaction of the polymer in powder form (pellets), followed by sintering. The sintering process consists on applying a heat treatment in the green specimens (after compaction), with maximum temperature above the melting point. This heat treatment is responsible for increasing the cohesion of the material, as well as, promotes the coalescence of the compressed grains – reducing the residual porosity of the compact to nearly zero – and interdiffusion of polymer chains between adjacent grains [1]. The application of filler with dimensions of the same magnitude of PTFE grains is commonly used to reinforce this material. This procedure is used due to difficulties in the manufacturing process and due to complex mechanism of deformation during the sintering of PTFE [2]. These fillers include short fibres [3], which are widely used – glass or carbon fibres added to granular PTFE,

before processing. To the authors' knowledge, there are few scientific contributions dealing to PTFE with continuous fibres as structural composite [4-7], and academic works rarely have described this type of composite in detail.

This work deals with the preparation of PTFE laminated composites. The composites were obtained by stacking bidirectional layers of PTFE with coated glass-fibre fabric, then, they were pressed and thermally treated. The Young's modulus and maximum stress of the material were evaluated as a function of the manufacturing parameters using three-point bending test and an adhesion test based on ASTM D3167-03a [8]. It is important to note that the adhesion test proposed by the authors is a new approach for evaluating the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A bidirectional type of commercial PTFE with coated glass-fibre fabric, Chemfab™ 013 STD – average thickness of 0.14 mm and fibre mass fraction of 38% – was used as raw material. This material was supplied by Saint-Gobain Ceramics & Plastics.

Test specimens were prepared by composite lamination process, which is made by stacking of the layers and cold-pressing, and subsequent heat treatment, called sintering in this work (Fig. 1). The step of stacking and pressing was performed by the deposition of layers of PTFE with coated glass-fibre fabric in a metallic die. After that, the laminate was pressed up to a controlled pressure P , then, it was removed from the die and submitted to sintering. This sintering process consists mainly on three stages: 1) raising the temperature at a constant heating rate (\dot{T}_H) to a temperature above the melting temperature called sintering temperature (T_s); 2) keeping at this temperature for a prescribed time (t_s) (sintering time); 3) cooling to a constant rate (\dot{T}_c) (Fig. 1). The sintering was carried out in an oven with computerized monitoring of the temperature, with maximum oscillation in control of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and internal circulation of air for forced convection, ensuring a range less than 2°C in the local where the specimens are individually sintered.

Figure 1 – Manufacturing process of the laminate composite made from the PTFE with coated glass-fibre fabric.

Three-point Bending Test

The specimens to three-point bending were tested using a support span (S) of 80 mm. This test was controlled by the displacement of the universal testing machine actuator and a constant speed of 0.25 mm/min was applied – corresponding to the absolute maximum strain rate value close to $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the bottom and top surfaces of the specimen –, in order to be low enough to neglect effects of viscosity. Flexural Young's modulus and maximum flexural strength are obtained based on stress-strain curves which are calculated by equations (1),

$$\sigma^f = \frac{3FS}{2W_s h_s^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon^f = \frac{6yh_s}{S^2} \quad (1)$$

where σ^f is the flexural stress, F is the reaction force in the actuator, ε^f is the flexural strain and y is the applied displacement. It is important to emphasise that these expressions are based on the assumption that the plane cross sections remain plane and normal to the longitudinal axis of symmetry. These equations are also valid for specimens with $h_s \ll S$ and for small strains with linear-elastic behaviour. These relationships were used to describe the stresses and strains during the test, in which the material is loaded to large deformations, showing non-linear behaviour and plasticity, but these approaches were considered acceptable for comparative purposes between specimens with different processing conditions.

Study of the Process Parameters

To study the influence of the process parameters on the mechanical behaviour of the laminates, the different values of P , T_s , t_s , and \dot{T}_c were investigated. Only the heating rate, \dot{T}_H , was not varied, because this parameter would have more influence in larger parts, due to the low thermal conductivity of PTFE [9]. Fig. (2) shows how these parameters were varied, and the best values (identified by the index x) corresponding to the best performance in the three-point bending test, considering the maximum flexural strength and flexural Young's modulus. The initial values of sintering parameters are shown in Table (1) and are based on the parameters of sintering used in the industry for products made for pure PTFE with the same dimensions of the specimens used in this work.

Table 1 – Typical values for the sintering parameters used in the industry for pure PTFE components with the same dimensions of specimens used in this work.

\dot{T}_H	T_s	t_s	\dot{T}_c
2°C/min	365°C	100 min	0.6°C/min

Figure 2 – Plan of experiments with variations of the pressing and sintering parameters.

Fibre-matrix Interactions

The mechanical properties of composites are affected by interlaminar PTFE-PTFE and fibre-matrix adhesion. Thus a test based on ASTM D3167 03a [10] was proposed by the authors to evaluate the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding. Specimens with 20 layers, 120 mm long and 15 mm width were manufactured for the adhesion tests. After sintering, the specimen was placed in a device developed for the test (like shown at Fig. 3a), which is coupled to the universal testing machine.

Influence of Residence Time with Temperature

Finally, in order to investigate specifically the influence of residence time with temperature on the mechanical properties of laminates, it was adopted a strategy based on a holding temperature (T) in the heating curve during a long time (Δt) (Fig. 3b). This strategy aims to estimate a critical temperature for a pronounced degradation of the fibre-matrix interface.

Figure 3 – a) illustration of the proposed test to evaluate the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding [10]; b) strategy for the study of the influence of residence time with temperature on the mechanical properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Study of the Process Parameters

The Young's modulus and maximum strength obtained by the three-point bending tests are shown in Fig. (4). The graph in Fig. (4a) shows that for specimens subjected to pressures of 11 and 22 MPa, the flexural Young's modulus ($E^f = \sigma^f / \varepsilon^f$) – obtained at the beginning of the loading – and maximum stress ($\sigma^{f(max)}$) – obtained by the maximum value of stress – were below the values found for the other curves. It can also be seen that these values are improved gradually with increasing pressure up to 54 MPa. Above this value, the gains in mechanical properties are small as observed for the values of 98 and 152 MPa (Fig. 4a). Thus, the value of pressure, P_x , of 54 MPa was chosen and maintained to manufacture the remaining specimens, following the test plan in Fig. (2).

Figure 4 – Stress-strain curves of three-point bending tests for specimens obtained from different manufacturing parameters: a) applied pressure; b) sintering temperature; c) sintering time; d) cooling rate.

The stress-strain curves for variation of sintering temperature, T_s , are represented by Fig. (4b). The worst results were found for the highest temperature (395°C). This temperature is near the temperature for initiation of degradation of the material [2] which may negatively influence the adhesion PTFE-PTFE and fibre-PTFE. The lowest temperatures, 350°C and 335°C, also lead to weak mechanical properties, because these temperatures are not high enough to allow complete bonding between layers of PTFE. The best result achieved was at 380°C, which was chosen to manufacture the remaining

specimens. The curves in Fig. (4c) show that the best outcome in terms of Young's modulus and maximum strength is for a sintering time of 5 min. According to Jahier [11], the ideal time for the sintering of parts – less than 3 mm of thickness – would be about 60 minutes if they are composed only by PTFE. Nevertheless, a relatively short time (5 min) was showed to be enough for sintering due considerable quantity of glass fibres ($\approx 38\%$ in mass fraction), which have higher thermal conductivity than PTFE. Results show worse performance for the larger sintering time. Although it is known that the interdiffusion of polymer chains of PTFE-PTFE is proportional to the sintering time [1], the short sintering time suggests that there is a mechanism that leads to a loss of adherence strength of fibre-matrix as the sintering time is increased.

The behaviour described was not observed in the initial phase of the three-point bending test for the specimen with the sintering time of 25 min (Fig. 4c). This specimen presented a performance below expected, which can be attributed to an accommodation of the original specimen due to be warped (probably induced during the sintering process), but, after that, slope of the curve and maximum stress followed the trend described by the other tests.

The time of cooling strongly influences the degree of PTFE crystallinity and it can have large influence on its mechanical behaviour. Fig. (4d) shows the stress-strain curves of three-point bending tests of specimens cooled at different rates. The results indicate that the highest cooling rate (namely, $0.6^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) provide the best values of Young's modulus and maximum strength. This value of cooling rate was the maximum allowed by the oven system. The degree of crystallinity of PTFE increases with the decrease of the cooling rate. According to Gangal [12], the bending modulus of elasticity increases with the degree of crystallinity by a factor of 5 when the crystallinity increases from 50 to 90%, with 0.2% void. This mechanical behaviour is observed for the PTFE matrix, but it is opposite to that obtained for the composite materials studied in this work. This phenomenon can also be explained by a mechanism that reduces strength in the fibre-matrix interface as a function of time when the material is submitted to high temperatures, since a lower cooling rate leads to a longer period of stay of specimens at these temperatures. This behaviour can be attributed to a degradation of fibres additives during the process of manufacturing [13]. Friedrich et al. [13] reported the possibility of withdraw the fibre additives during burning process. A change in colour (bleaching) of the material was observed when it was submitted to high temperatures for a long time, which may indicate the burning of these additives.

For the specimens in which other sintering parameters were modified, as discussed before, the degradation of the interface might have also influenced the results, both in the case of very high temperatures (395°C), when the degradation of the interface would be accelerated, and in the cases in which specimens are submitted for a very long time.

According to the study presented, the best values of each parameter were initially obtained a structural improvement of the composite, taking into account variations providing in their manufacturing process (Table (2)). The flexural Young's modulus was 12.3 GPa to the specimens made according to the chosen values manufacturing – much higher than the value of 0.67 GPa for PTFE – and the maximum strength was 81 MPa.

Table 2 – Sintering parameters chosen according to the methodology applied which resulted in better performance of the material.

P	T_s	t_s	\dot{T}_c
54 MPa	380°C	5 min	0.6°C/min

Fibre-matrix Interactions

In order to analyse the influence of fibre-matrix interactions, four sets of parameters studied were chosen – including the worst and the best sets of parameters – (Table 3). For this, an adhesion test was proposed and performed (Fig. 3a) and the results are shown in Fig. (5a). The Fig. (5b) shows the stress-strain curves obtained by three-point bending tests to these sets of parameters. Comparison of the tests shows a correlation between the strength of pullout testing of adhesion and the mechanical properties by three-point bending tests (Table 3).

The results indicate that the adhesion between the layers strongly influences the laminated mechanical properties. These results confirm the earlier hypothesis that residence time at high temperatures is the factor that most contributes to the degradation of the fibre-matrix interface. According to Oshima et al. [6] the fibres additives might have been eliminated because the long time of the material at high temperatures causes micro-defects and /or voids between the fibres and matrix. The comparison of combined results between the three-point bending and adhesion tests (Fig. 5 and Table 3), indicating that the fibre-matrix interface is the major responsible for the failure.

Figure 5 – a) bond strength tests; b) three-point bending.

Table 3: Process parameters, three-point bending and bond strength tests.

Cases, cf. Fig. (5)	Manufacturing				Three-point bending test		Mean bond test
	P	T_s [°C]	t_s [min]	\dot{T}_c [°C/min]	E_f [GPa]	$\sigma^{f(max)}$ [MPa]	Load [N]
1	54	380	5	0.6	12.3	81	10.3
2	54	335	100	0.6	10.4	60	8.1
3	54	380	5	0.05	10.4	46	6.4
4	54	380	1000	0.6	10.5	44	6.0

To verify the critical temperature of fibre-matrix interface degradation, seven specimens were made with manufacturing parameters values described in Table 4. All the specimens follow the same curve of sintering and remain at different holding temperatures T during a time Δt of 1000 min.

The Fig. (6a) shows the stress-strain curves obtained by three-points bending tests. The Fig (6b) shows the maximum stress as a function of the holding temperature T and shows a sharp drop in temperature to levels exceeding 335°C. Temperature of 350°C was chosen critical.

Influence of Residence Time with Temperature

In order to check the influence of residence time above the critical temperature in maximum strength, the time above this critical temperature was estimated following the strategy indicated by Fig. (7). In the Fig. (8) is shown an interpolation curve of the points of maximum strength for all specimens that were subjected to temperatures above the critical temperature (350°C) during sintering, disregarding that ones where the pressure was different of 54 MPa.

Table 4 – Manufacturing parameters and values of the three-point bending test to study the influence of time and temperature in mechanical properties.

Cases	Manufacturing Parameters - cf. Fig. (3b) and Fig. (6)							
	P [MPa]	\dot{T}_H [°C/min]	T_s [°C]	t_s [min]	\dot{T}_c [°C/min]	Δt [min]	T [°C]	
1	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	25	
2	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	50	
3	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	150	
4	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	310	
5	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	335	
6	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	365	
7	54	2	380	5	0.6	1000	380	

Figure 6 - Results obtained by three-point bending test to study the influence of time and temperature: a) stress-strain curves; b) maximum strength for stress-strain curves as a function of the holding temperature.

Figure 7 – Scheme to estimate the residence time of each specimen above the critical temperature.

Figure 8 - Trend line of the maximum strength for the residence time above the critical temperature.

Based on this study, strategies of manufacturing laminates made from fabric Chemfab™ 013 STD can be suggested, where the material would remain only enough time for PTFE sintering at high temperatures, with a rapid cooling before the beginning of crystallization and only a slow cooling during crystallization.

CONCLUSIONS

This study showed the feasibility of manufacturing composite laminates for structural use of a PTFE matrix with continuous glass fibres, using commercial PTFE-coated glass-fibre fabric. Considerable gain was obtained in stiffness and mechanical strength in comparison with the products made from pure PTFE. The methodology that was used provided preliminary understanding of how the parameters considered for pressing and sintering influence the mechanical properties of this composite. The test plan developed and implemented provided a preliminary response on the influence of these parameters and the associated adhesion test has shown that the fibre-matrix adhesion – which is difficult to obtain due to the nature of the PTFE – is the major responsible for the change of mechanical behaviour studied here, highlighting the need for optimization of the manufacturing process to obtain better responses, in addition to seeking improvements with respect to the fibre-matrix interface.

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